

immerse

INTEGRATION MAPPING OF REFUGEE
AND MIGRANT CHILDREN

IMMERSE D3.2_V2.2

IMMERSE DELIVERABLE D3.2

HANDBOOK FOR THE IMMERSE DATA COLLECTION FIELDWORK

VERSION 2.2

Contract No: 822536

Summary

This document is a guide to the practical execution of fieldwork for the large-scale data collection phase of the IMMERSE project. It provides guidelines and suggestions for arranging, conducting, and following-up visits to data collection sites, such as schools and reception centres. Alternate data collection strategies to accommodate restrictions due to Covid-19 are also suggested.

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This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822536

Deliverable Nr.	3.2	Work Package Nr.	WP3	Task/s Nr.	T3.3
Work Package Title	Data Collection and Monitoring				
Linked Task/s Title	T3.3 Data Collection				
Status	Draft	(Draft/Draft Final/Final)			
Dissemination level	PU	(PU-Public, PP, RE-Restricted, CO-Confidential)			
Due date deliverable	M18	Submission date	M23		
Deliverable version	2.2				

Approval status

FUNCTION	NAME	DATE	SIGNATURE
Deliverable responsible	UCC		
WP leader	UCC		
Project coordinator	Comillas		

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Document History

Version	Date	Comment
1.0	28 August	
2.0	10 September	
2.1	15 September	
2.2	19 October	

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Handbook for the IMMERSE Data Collection Fieldwork

1 Executive summary

This document is a practical guide for the large-scale data collection phase of the IMMERSE project. It provides guidelines for site visits and is divided into four sections. The first three sections cover in-person fieldwork, which is the ideal scenario, and outline suggested procedures for pre-site visit activity, activity during the site visit, and post-site visit activity. Given current conditions related to Covid-19, however, we recognise that in-person site visits may not always be possible. The fourth section therefore outlines alternatives that do not require the researchers to be physically present at the site: 'virtual' site visits and open time frame data collection.

The first section deals with site visit preparation, beginning with recruitment of schools and other data collection environments. It goes on to discuss arranging the site visit, including the critical task of classroom sampling (if data collection is in a school), which must be coordinated with the principal or other designated site representatives. A final pre-site visit checklist is suggested, comprised of tasks and materials that are likely to be helpful in ensuring preparedness.

The second section covers activities during the site visit, in-person and virtual, beginning with maintaining a logbook of vital details from site visits. This section includes suggested scripts for introducing the questionnaires, directs researchers to user guides for the data collection platform, troubleshooting suggestions for common problems, and options for participant debriefing sessions. The third section focuses on tasks to be carried out after the site visit, including research team debriefing, data monitoring, and participant follow-up.

The fourth section provides alternatives and adjustments to the in-person site visit plan if Covid-19 (or other circumstances) prevents researchers from being physically present at research sites. We outline 'virtual' site visits, where data is collected from the children at the site, and the researcher is present via a video conference platform or on the phone, and open time frame data collection, which involves no visit, and where participants complete their questionnaires at their convenience within a given time frame.

While it is important that we keep fieldwork relatively consistent across the IMMERSE partner countries, each country will have particularities that need to be accommodated, particularly given different sites' policies around visitors/guests and Covid-19 restrictions. The Handbook is intended to supply an overall structure to data collection, rather than being a definitive and detailed step-by-step manual to be strictly adhered to. It is therefore written in general terms, and partners should feel free to adapt the guidelines and suggestions provided here to their country and data collection environment contexts as appropriate.

2 Pre-Site Visit

2.1 Recruitment

2.1.1 Introductory contact

Once you have selected schools using the stratified random sampling technique or selected non-formal environments using the purposive sampling technique (see *D3.1 Report on Standardisation across Implementation of Data Collection*), you can begin recruiting these sites to participate in the study.¹ In cases where you already have a contact at the site, please do make use of this advantage. In many cases, however, you will not personally know anyone at the site. We suggest making first contact via either phone or email and recommend contacting the principal (or equivalent in the case of non-formal centres) directly if possible. Here are some important pieces of information you may want to include in your introduction:

- Clear identification of yourself and your organisation – let the site know that the request is coming from a legitimate party
- Name the study in full and state the funding source – this also helps to confer legitimacy, may also help to make clear that the study is not undertaken on behalf of the government and is not for the purposes of evaluation
- Very brief explanation of the study – clear and concise, don't overload with detail
- Explain why the site's participation would be of great help to the project
- Reassurance that participation will not be a burden to the site (in terms of time, resources, etc.)
- Offer to keep them updated on project progress, share results, etc.
- Let them know the name of the ethics board who approved the project (if applicable)
- Provide contact details of a designated person on your team and project website address

We recommend designating one or two people on your team to handle all communication related to fieldwork. They will be responsible for handling any inquiries relating to the project and for arranging the site visits, so it must be someone who is able to check email/voicemail regularly and respond in a timely fashion (i.e. within 24-48 hours).

You may also want to attach or offer to send an information sheet with more detail about the project or better yet include the project's website so that your introductory communication can stay short and to the point. You can find an information sheet in the IMMERSE Google Drive, (WP3 folder) that you can download and attach as PDF. You may start to compile frequently asked questions and use these for future recruitment once you start to get some responses and a sense of what the most common concerns the sites have about participating.

Below is a sample introductory email/script template and the adaptation for an Irish primary school. You can use this as a guide, or you can write your own.

¹ Please note that if your institution requires you to undergo an ethics review, this should be completed and approval obtained before any formal recruitment takes place.

SAMPLE INTRODUCTORY EMAIL - TEMPLATE

Dear Principal [or equivalent in non-formal settings, try to address by name if possible],

We are contacting you about a European research project being conducted by [name of your university/organisation] examining the experiences of migrant and refugee children in [host country] schools as part of a larger European project, Integration Mapping of Migrant and Refugee Children (IMMERSE), that has been funded by the European Commission. With the support of the [if you have the approval of an official/governmental body for IMMERSE, definitely mention it here], we are contacting you about your school's potential participation in IMMERSE, and we hope you will consider our request.

Your school's participation

Gathering data from children, parents, and schools is the next crucial phase of IMMERSE, and we are looking for schools to become part of the [host country] sample for data collection. Your school has been randomly selected from a list of [list basic selection criteria here that the school falls into, e.g. small/big, rural/urban, religious/non-religious] schools in [name the region/city here, e.g. Cork/Dublin/Limerick], [and list any additional screening criteria you may need from the school to gauge their eligibility for the study, e.g. if your student population includes at least 20% migrant and/or refugee children], we invite you and your students to participate in our survey. (By migrant children, we mean those who were born outside of Ireland or have at least one parent born outside of Ireland).

Participation involves selecting several classes from [list the year groups you want to survey from that school, e.g. 1st/3rd/5th years in your school] to fill out a questionnaire, preferably online. There are also online questionnaires for the principal and teachers. We will provide a link to send to parents so they can give consent online and fill out a short questionnaire themselves. If parents give consent, we can collect data from the children during a one-time in-person visit of approximately [3-4 hours or one-half day] from our researchers. We will work with you to arrange the visit at the [site]'s convenience and ensure this takes as little time and causes as little disruption to normal activities as possible. We will provide detailed information about the survey and how the data will be collected, stored, and analysed.

If [list additional screen criteria here again if needed, e.g. your student population includes at least 20% migrant or refugee children, and] you are interested in having your [school/centre] participate in this important and timely research, please contact a member of our research team, [give contact person name and contact details]. A response at this point does not oblige you to take part in the survey, it just indicates interest in being part of our study [and that your school meets the 20% threshold, or whatever extra screening criteria you may need].

About the Project – IMMERSE

IMMERSE is a Horizon 2020 project funded by the European Commission involving research teams in 6 countries – Ireland, Spain, Italy, Greece, Germany, and Belgium. The [host country] research team is based at [name of your university/organisation]. Please see the attached information sheet for more details on the project, and how your school's participation would contribute to its next critical phase.

Questions? Ask us!

If you have any questions or would like more information on the survey or the larger research project, please do not hesitate to contact us. We would be very happy to address any questions and/or concerns

you may have via email, arrange a phone call or and in-person meeting. You can also visit the project's website: <https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/>.

Your Sincerely,

[list all relevant team members and their positions, especially the Primary Investigator]

SAMPLE INTRODUCTORY EMAIL – IRISH PRIMARY SCHOOL

Dear Principal O'Dowd,

We are contacting you about a European research project being conducted by researchers at University College Cork examining the experiences of migrant and refugee children in Irish schools as part of a larger European project, Integration Mapping of Migrant and Refugee Children (IMMERSE), that has been funded by the European Commission. With the support of the Department of Education and Skills, we are contacting you about your school's potential participation in IMMERSE, and we hope you will consider our request.

Your school's participation

Gathering data from children is the next crucial phase of IMMERSE, and we are looking for schools to become part of the Irish sample for data collection. Your school has been randomly selected from a list of DEIS Catholic schools in Dublin, and if your student population includes at least 25% migrant and/or refugee children, we invite you and your students to participate in our survey. (By migrant children, we mean those who were born outside of Ireland or have at least one parent born outside of Ireland).

Participation involves selecting several classes from 1st, 3rd, and 5th years in your school to fill out a questionnaire, preferably online. There are also online questionnaires for the principal and teachers. We will provide a link to send to parents so they can give consent online and fill out a short questionnaire themselves. If parents give consent, we can collect data from the children during a one-time in-person visit of approximately [3-4 hours or one-half day] from our researchers. We will work with you to arrange the visit at the school's convenience and ensure this takes as little time and causes as little disruption to normal activities as possible. We will provide detailed information about the survey and how the data will be collected, stored, and analysed.

If your student population includes at least 25% migrant or refugee background children, and you are interested in having your school participate in this important and timely research, please contact a member of our research team – Reana Maier, reana.maier@ucc.ie. A response at this point does not oblige you to take part in the survey, it just indicates interest in being part of our study and that your school meets the 25% threshold for migrant and/or refugee background students.

About the Project – IMMERSE

IMMERSE is a Horizon 2020 project funded by the European Commission involving research teams in 6 countries – Ireland, Spain, Italy, Greece, Germany, and Belgium. The Irish research team is based at University College Cork in partnership with the Institute for Social Sciences in the 21st Century. The study has been approved by the UCC Social Research Ethics Committee and all fieldwork researchers have been garda vetted. Please see the attached information sheet for more details on the project, and how your school's participation would contribute to its next critical phase.

Questions? Ask us!

If you have any questions or would like more information on the survey or the larger research project, please do not hesitate to contact us. We would be very happy to address any questions and/or concerns you may have via email, arrange a phone call or an in-person meeting. You can also visit the project's website: <https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/>.

Your Sincerely,

Shirley Martin – Primary Investigator

Deirdre Horgan – Co-Investigator

Jacqui O’Riordan – Co-Investigator

Reana Maier – Postdoctoral Researcher, reana.maier@ucc.ie

If you get a positive response, great! You can go ahead with arranging the visit. If you get a negative response, thank them for their time and leave them with the contact information again in case they have further interest later.

2.1.2 Follow-up to initial invitation to participate

In some cases, you will not receive any response to the invitation, either positive or negative. In these cases, your team should decide on a reasonable timeframe (we would suggest 1-2 weeks) after which to follow-up with the site. Follow-ups can be done initially by email or phone, but in-person is usually the most effective method, if it is possible, so we suggest trying to set up a meeting with the principal or equivalent. Should an in-person meeting not be possible, concerns can be addressed through online communications. In any event, follow-ups should be short and encouraging, offering to discuss any concerns or questions via email, phone call, video conference, or at an in-person meeting. Your team should decide how many follow-up attempts you will make to non-responsive sites, after which you will move on to the next site on your recruitment list. A member of your team should be allocated to log details of contact/responses so that there is no duplication of invitations and follow-ups.

2.2 Arranging the Site Visit

2.2.1 Organising your calendar

Keeping an up-to-date fieldwork calendar that is accessible to all the relevant members of the team is of critical importance, and we suggest designating someone to be responsible for this. You may want to include information about team member schedules on this calendar, so that the person working with the site to arrange the site visit will know when other team members are or are not available for fieldwork.

2.2.2 Classroom sampling

If you are collecting data from a school, a key part of the data collection will be classroom sampling. For a full description of this, see D3.1, section 4.3. You will need to gather some information from the principal (or whoever is helping you arrange the site visit) in order to do your classroom sampling:

- Average class size (approximate is fine)
- How many classes there are in each year group from which you want to collect data
- Whether classes are deliberately grouped according to any characteristic (e.g. ability)

If there are only 1-2 classes in each year group, then you will probably want to collect data from the whole year group, but if there are three or more, you will need to randomly select two, provided they are not very small classes and provided they are not deliberately grouped. If the classes are very small, then you may want to collect data from more than two. Refer to D3.1, section 4.3 to see how to select from classes that are deliberately grouped.

2.2.3 Site codes

The anonymised participant ID codes for the main database will include some numbers that indicate the site at which the data from that participant was collected. As such, you need to assign each site a different number code. Each site code should be two digits (so range from 00 to 99) and be assigned randomly to the site (e.g. site 02 = Hogwarts, site 59 = Xavier's School for Gifted Youngsters, etc.). Don't worry about accidentally choosing a code that is the same as the site code from another country, because the participant codes that are automatically generated by the online data collection system will also contain characters indicating country and region (see Appendix A for an explanation of the participant ID codes). Your team should keep a record that indicates which site each number you have assigned relates to, but this record should not be shared outside your team or appear in any official documentation. This is just for your team's records and can be destroyed when you destroy the personal data after completion of the study.

In addition, you will need to assign a class code to each class for school research sites. These should be two-digit numbers (01, 02, 36, etc.), and you can use the same ones for different sites, because these will not make up part of the ID code. So, for example, say we are giving the questionnaire to 6 classes of students from site 02. You could call these classes 01, 02, 03, 04, 05, and 06. Which class gets which class code is up to your team and is also just for your team's records.

When you send the consent form link to the site to send on to the parents (and teachers/principals if applicable), you will need to include the site code and the class code (if it is a school).

2.2.4 Scheduling the site visit

Ideally, all data collection with the children would be done via in-person site visits, where the researchers are present at the site while the children are filling out their questionnaires (either online or PAP). For various reasons, not least of which is Covid-19 restrictions, this will not always be possible. If in-person visits are not possible, guidelines and suggestions for 'virtual' visits and remote data collection are in Section 5. If there are sites where in-person visits are the only data collection option (i.e. virtual/remote data collection is not possible), but access to these is restricted due to Covid, it may be necessary to delay data collection until sometime in 2021 in the hope that conditions will allow researchers to be present.

If you are able to conduct site visits in person, scheduling these visits requires careful attention. Depending on how many team members you have, you may be able to conduct visits at two sites simultaneously, but if your team is small, you will probably be limited to data collection from one site at a time. Taking into

account travel, the amount of time it will take to collect data in a site, and researcher resources, we do not recommend scheduling more than 1-2 site visits in a day. Fieldwork is a demanding, high-energy undertaking that is surprisingly tiring. We encourage your team to plan site visits with this in mind, if possible.

Work with the site to schedule the site visit for days and times that will be convenient for them and hopefully to avoid any events that would mean a number of students would be absent that day (e.g. class trips). Ensure that you know exactly where the site is and approximately how long it will take to get there. This is especially important if any of the researchers are relying on public transportation to get to and from the site. We recommend scheduling site visits at least 2-3 weeks in advance to allow the site time to send parents the link to the consent form, to allow parents to give consent and to fill out their own questionnaires.

HELPFUL INFORMATION TO GATHER FROM THE SITE

In addition to information on classes for classroom sampling, there are other things you will need to gather from the person who is helping you arrange an in-person site visit. You can create a checklist or google form if you think this will be helpful:

- Does the site need PAP consent forms/parent questionnaires? If the site does not have an email distribution list of parents or parents are unlikely to be able to get online to give consent and fill out their questionnaire, you will need to arrange for PAP forms to be delivered to the site and distributed to parents (check with site about appropriate languages).
- Approximately how many participants in total you will be collecting data from on the day of the site visit. This is so you can judge the amount of time the site visit will take and possibly how many researchers will be needed for the visit. You also need to know this in order to bring sufficient pen-and-paper (PAP) back-up questionnaires. For the PAP back-ups, check with the school to see which languages would be useful to bring.
- What technology the school has available for the online data collection – computers, laptops, tablets – including what technology the students themselves may bring.
- Whether there is a stable wifi connection. If the site does not have a wifi connection, that's okay, there is an offline data collection platform, but this can only be used if your research team has tablets on which the offline app can be downloaded ahead of time. There are also a few extra steps that researchers will need to do pre- and post-site visit in these cases.
- Who is the contact person at the site if one of the children experiences distress during the data collection and any site policies related to this
- Where in the site the data collection will take place – a computer lab, a meeting room, library, classrooms
- What policies or procedures the site may have in relation to Covid-19, such as a health checklist or temperature checks before researchers will be allowed to enter the site

In addition to this information to be gathered from the site, your team should prepare a list of local resources for parent, principal, and teacher participants should they experience any distress while participating. You may not need to use them, but you should be prepared to provide them.

2.2.5 Sending links for parent consent and principal/teacher questionnaires

Once you have arranged all the details for the site visit/data collection, you can create the needed consent forms in the online data collection system for parents (and teachers and principal, if the site is a school) and send these links to the site, so that they can forward them to the parents/guardians of the children selected (and principal/teachers) to participate. Remember that you have to incorporate the “survey” code into the landing page link so that the participants get the right consent forms.

We suggest asking parents, principals and teachers to have their questionnaires filled in by the day of the site visit. Parental/guardian consent is necessary in order for children to participate. While it is not strictly necessary for principals and teachers to have finished their questionnaires by the time the children go to fill in theirs, it will be easier for your team if all data collection from a site can be completed by the end of the site visit. This will hopefully, save you from having to chase teachers and principals to fill in their questionnaires days and weeks after you’ve gathered data from the children.

2.3 Pre-site Visit Checklist

Sometime before the site visit, especially before the first few site visits, we suggest having a meeting with the team members who will be doing data collection to go over logistics and ensure all necessary materials will be available. A pre-site visit checklist may be helpful in this regard. Below are some suggested items to include.

- Location of site confirmed
- Date and time of visit confirmed with site 24-48 hours ahead of visit
- Travel to and from site for all members of research team is coordinated
- Check online to see whether parental consents have been given (authorizations page)
- Check with school for PAP parental consent, where necessary
- Review the timeline of the site visit
- Assign responsibilities to members of research team
- Check materials needed and decide who will bring what
- Make sure tablets are charged and have the offline app (called Form Box, see <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1QnPzllrsb7uNvAMaS9CBeiG56EN4iHXS/view>), and questionnaires already downloaded (in case they need to work offline)
- Ensure that research team members are familiar with and comply with all public health guidelines pertaining to sites to be visited.

Suggested site visit inventory items (largely for in-person site visit)

- Tablets and chargers
- PAP questionnaire back-ups
- Paper child assent form back-ups
- Extra copies of IMMERSE information sheet
- Pens/pencils
- Name of contact person at site and of designated person if child experiences distress during the study
- Site visit log (see next section)

3 During the Site Visit

3.1 Site Logbook

We strongly recommend keeping a logbook of site visits for your own records, noting the site (and the site code you have assigned to it), location (keep this general, no need for exact addresses), the date and time of arrival and departure (if appropriate), names of the research team, name of key contact person at the site, very brief description of basic activities that took place during the site visit, and whether any problems occurred during the visit. This log can be kept in a notebook or digitally but should be stored securely (we recommend a password protected folder) since it will contain the site names and codes. You can use the template below (which we have filled out as an example) or create your own. It is advisable to allocate the monitoring of this responsibility to a specific team member.

SAMPLE SITE VISIT LOGBOOK ENTRY FOR IN-PERSON VISITS

Site Visit Logbook Entry # 18	
Site: Hogwarts	Site code: 02
Date: 23 November, 2020	Location: Dublin
Research team: Reana, Jacqui, Deirdre	
Time of arrival at site: 9:30am	Time of departure from site: 12:30pm

Group No.	No. of part's	Year/ age group	Length of time to complete questionnaire	Length of time for debrief	Problems arising	How problems were addressed
1	25	1st year (12/13 year olds)	40 minutes	5 minutes	Trouble understanding Q. X	Explained using alternate language
2	30	3 rd year (14/15 year olds)	40 minutes	5 minutes	Log in page wouldn't work	Reloaded site
3	20	5 th year (16/17 year olds)	35 minutes	5 minutes		

Problems can relate to any aspect of the site visit – logistics, understanding and interpretation of the questionnaire, technology, ethics. Report technological problems to IECISA (immerse_support@iecisa.com), report problems with questionnaire content to UCC and Comillas, and keep track of any ethical issues that arise to document in progress reports for the European Commission. Any significant ethical issues that could not be solved within your team should be reported to Comillas within 48 hours of the site visit.

When you arrive at the site, be sure to confirm with the person who is coordinating your visit who the designated contact person is if a child experiences distress and how that person can be contacted quickly. We recommend, if possible, arriving at the site with enough time to set up the space in which the data

collection will take place so that when the participants arrive, you can go straight into introducing the study and questionnaires.

3.2 Administering the Survey

3.2.1 Introductory script

When you have a group of participants ready, a standard script of introductory remarks can help get the session going. You can start by introducing yourself and the research team and telling the participants what organisation you are from. Tell them a little bit about the project and why their participation is so important, in age-appropriate language. Explain what they will be doing and let them know what to do if they have questions. It is important to reassure participants that their participation will be anonymous and that there are no right or wrong answers to the questions. You can use the sample script below or write one of your own.

SAMPLE INTRODUCTORY SCRIPT

Hello everyone! Thank you very much for being here today. My name is [your name here], and I'm a researcher at [name of your organisation]. These are my fellow researchers, [names of team members], and we're here today because we need your help.

We're working on a study that looks at what makes children feel like they belong in school, especially children who have moved to a new country and a new school. This study is taking place in six different countries across Europe – Spain, Italy, Greece, Germany, Belgium, and Ireland – and will gather information from thousands of children. From all that information, we'll be able to help make school a more fun and welcoming place to be for everyone.

What we're asking you to do today is answer a bunch of questions for us. We have already asked your parents about this and they are happy for you to answer our questions. Some of those questions will be about you and your family, some of them will be about your school, and some of them will be about your feelings and experiences. We don't record your name, so all of your answers will be anonymous – no one will know it was you who gave them. There are no right or wrong answers, either, you just answer whatever is right for you.

If you have any questions along the way, you can ask me or any of the team. Does anyone have any questions now?

Great, let's get started! If you look at the screen in front of you, you will see the welcome page for the questionnaire. You need to enter your authorization code (which you would have gotten from your parents), and then you can begin. . . .

3.2.2 Start screen for questionnaires

We recommend having all devices being used for data collection to be already on the right page before the children come into the room. Each country will have distinct links to the questionnaires, and these links will

be provided to you by IECISA. Participants will need an authorization code to enter on the first page of the questionnaire, which they should have received from their parents (automatically generated after parent gives consent). If the child participant does not have her/his code, it can be obtained from the Authorizations tab in the researcher portal of the online data collection system.

3.2.3 Administering the questionnaires in PAP form

If you are in a site where there is no technology available or the technology ceases to work properly, you will have to administer the questionnaires via the PAP back-ups. We cannot count on the sites being willing to accommodate a second visit if our technology fails, so this is why it is always necessary to bring PAP questionnaires with you, even if it seems like a hassle to cart around. If you provided PAP parent consent forms and questionnaires to the site for parents who did not have access to technology and had to complete these manually, make sure to collect them from the principal or whoever is holding them for you.

There isn't much difference between completing the questionnaire online vs. PAP for the participant. Remind the participants not to write their name anywhere on the questionnaire (but make sure they fill in their authorization code!) and ask them to mark their answers clearly.

The major difference with the PAP questionnaires is that once the site visit is completed, the data will have to be manually input into the central database by someone on the research team (see section 4.2.2 below).

3.2.4 Troubleshooting during the site visit

No matter how carefully we plan, things can always go wrong during fieldwork. We've tried to anticipate some of the issues that may arise during site visits for IMMERSE and provide some guidance on how to solve them.

PARTICIPANT DISTRESS

If a participant becomes distressed during the study, you should contact the person the site has designated for this situation. If this person is not available or the site did not designate someone, contact the person who coordinated the site visit. This will not be a likely scenario in most sites, but we will be dealing with some children who have experienced very traumatic things, and research teams need to be prepared for the possibility that the questionnaire may bring up difficult memories or feelings, however unlikely this is.

DIFFICULTY IN UNDERSTANDING QUESTIONNAIRE CONTENT

If a participant does not understand something in the questionnaire, do your best to explain or use alternative terms. Make a note of the situation in your site log and report this to UCC (reana.maier@ucc.ie). If we encounter a recurring problem across many sites, we may look at adjusting the instrument or at the very least circulate the problem and a solution to all partners. During the pilot phase, we will keep a similar record of any difficulties with questionnaire content and, if needed, distribute a list of common ones so that your team can be prepared to answer questions on those survey items.

PROBLEMS WITH THE DATA COLLECTION PLATFORM

The user guide for the online data collection platform can be found here, in the IMMERSE google drive: https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1N_URbL31nEX-vx7Y-0dPkCOWDIgdQ4jM. Tutorial videos are also

available in the google drive, and there will be an FAQ group in the Hub to address technical concerns. It is possible, though unlikely, that you may be able to contact someone from IECISA (immerse_support@iecisa.com) while you are at the site to help. If the problem cannot be solved quickly, you will have to administer the questionnaire in the PAP form.

COVID 19

If the research team is able to make an in-person visit, they may need to provide reassurance to the school that all team members are well. It is imperative that research team members closely follow health guidelines, keep appropriate distances from staff and children in schools/informal settings and agree to specific health advice of sites. Also, it is important that they have taken all necessary precautions, are masked and that any tablets brought into the school have been sanitised, etc.

3.2.5 Post-questionnaire debrief

Once your group of participants have finished their questionnaires, we recommend a short debriefing to end the session. Thank the participants for their time and leave contact details if anyone has questions or wants to access supports.

3.3 Exiting the Site

Upon completing the data collection, it might be useful to consult your site visit inventory to ensure that all your materials are collected, especially tablets and chargers. Be sure to thank the person who coordinated the site visit and leave them with your contact information should they have any questions or concerns. Advise them that you will follow-up in a few days to make sure everything is alright and on how to keep updated on the project's progress.

4 Post-Site Visit

4.1 Research Team Debrief

We recommend a research team debriefing after each site visit, especially after the first few site visits, to allow the team to discuss how the site visit went and whether any adjustments to the process are needed. This debriefing would ideally take place immediately following the site visit or at least within a day or two so that the memory of it is still fresh in the mind. Any problems that occurred during the data collection can be reflected on (and reported to UCC, Comillas, or IECISA if needed) and solutions considered. Teams should also designate a team member to be responsible for data monitoring and follow-up contact.

4.2 Data Monitoring

There are three tasks associated with post-site visit data monitoring.

4.2.1 Manual upload of data and deletion from devices in offline mode

If you had any participants who completed their questionnaires on a device in offline mode, the data needs to be uploaded to the database when the device re-connects to wifi. There is a video here:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1QnPzllrsb7uNvAMaS9CBeiG56EN4iHXS/view?usp=sharing> that shows how to “sync” the data on the tablet with the main database. After you have checked that the upload was successful, you must delete the data off the device. It is critically important that we do not have questionnaire data being stored long-term on devices.

4.2.2 Manual input of data from PAP questionnaires

If you had any participants who completed PAP questionnaires, you must manually input their data into the database. The easiest way to do this is to open up the appropriate questionnaire online and fill it in according to the answers on the paper. This will result in far fewer transposition errors than filling in the database directly. Another option is to enter the information directly into the response spreadsheet (accessible through your country’s google account/drive, click on the appropriate questionnaires, click on “responses” on the top, click on the green icon in the top right). If you enter information into the spreadsheet directly, you must be *very, very precise* and enter it exactly as it appears in for the other participants. Typos, extra spaces, missing spaces or punctuation, etc. will result in the data not being recognised later when it comes to the analysis.

The PAP copies of the questionnaires and consent forms should be stored in a locked cabinet or otherwise secured location and destroyed along with the personal data after the appropriate amount of elapsed time after the completion of the project.

4.2.3 Data check

Even if all your participants were able to complete their questionnaires online on devices that were connected to wifi, it is still a good idea to check the data to make sure that the data successfully uploaded to the database and does not contain errors. To check the data, you need to go into your team’s google account, go into the Google Form for the questionnaire you are interested in, and download the responses as an excel sheet. You don’t have to go through it in fine detail, line by line, but a quick check is advised to make sure everything looks right and there isn’t missing data. If you see anything that does not look right, notify IECISA and UCC right away. UCC is responsible for more in-depth data monitoring over the course of the data collection, but it will be useful to have the teams keeping an eye on their own data along the way, too.

4.3 Follow-ups and Thank Yous

The information sheets we give to all our participants indicate that we will check in with them after data collection in case participating has caused any distress. With the children and young people, this is done immediately after they have finished filling in the questionnaires. For parents, principals, and teachers, this will be done after the site visit via email. These follow-up emails should be short and cheerful, expressing thanks for participating in the study and offering direction to resources should the participant find themselves in need of support. To be clear, we are not offering to support the participant ourselves in their distress – we are not qualified to do this. However, as indicated in the pre-site visit section, each team should have compiled a list of support resources that the participants can access if they need to. Sample emails for parents and principals/teachers are below. The email to principals can be sent to the principal directly, and the email to parents and teachers should be sent via the school, like the initial invitation to

participate. Even though we technically would have their email addresses at this point, it is important that we protect their privacy and do not use them for any purpose.

In addition, these follow-ups should direct the participant to our website, Youtube channel, Facebook page, etc. and offer to keep them updated on the project's progress. This would also be a good opportunity to direct their attention to the Hub and encourage them to join this community.

SAMPLE FOLLOW-UP EMAIL TO PARENTS

Dear Parents/Guardians,

On behalf of the entire IMMERSE Research Consortium, thank you so much for participating and for allowing your children to participate in IMMERSE! The information you and your children have provided is fundamental to the success of the project – we would not be able to make positive contributions to school and government policy without it.

What happens next? The survey answers you and your child provided will join the answers of hundreds of other parents and children, plus survey answers from principals and teachers, in [Ireland] and thousands of other parents, children, principals, and teachers across Europe. Once we have finished collecting all of our data, which should be around October 2021, we will use this rich and varied database to look at the relationships between positive outcomes for children in schools and the family and school factors that help improve those outcomes. Our final reports are set to be submitted to the European Commission late in 2022.

What should I do if I am feeling unsettled because of the survey? If there has been any disruption or distress caused by participating in IMMERSE, there is a list of local support resources at the end of this letter that may be of help to you.

Where can I follow the project's progress? There are a number of ways to follow IMMERSE's progress. We have a project website (www.immerse-h2020.eu), Facebook page (<https://www.facebook.com/Immerse.H2020>), Twitter account (@IMMERSE_H2020), Youtube channel (IMMERSE_H2020), and an Instagram account (immerse_h2020). We also have an interactive community called the IMMERSE Hub that you can join via the website. This is a place for people to share information and resources around schools and integration.

How can I get involved? If you would like to get involved in or become better informed about issues of education and integration, the IMMERSE website features the IMMERSE Hub, an online community where people can join groups and share and discuss knowledge, ideas, methods, and resources. You can register in the Hub from the IMMERSE main website.

Thank you and best wishes from the IMMERSE [Ireland team at University College Cork]!

Shirley Martin – Primary Investigator
Deirdre Horgan – Co-Investigator
Jacqui O'Riordan – Co-Investigator
Reana Maier – Postdoctoral Researcher

Support Resources in [Ireland]:

[list of resources and contact information here, about 3-5 organisations]

SAMPLE FOLLOW-UP EMAIL TO PRINCIPALS/TEACHERS

Dear Parents/Guardians,

On behalf of the entire IMMERSE Research Consortium, thank you so much for participating in IMMERSE! The information you have provided is fundamental to the success of the project – we would not be able to make positive contributions to school and government policy without it.

What happens next? The survey answers you provided will join the answers of other principals, teachers, parents, and children in [Ireland] and thousands of other principals, teachers, parents, and children across Europe. Once we have finished collecting all of our data, which should be around October 2021, we will use this rich and varied database to look at the relationships between positive outcomes for children in schools and the family and school factors that help improve those outcomes. Our final reports are set to be submitted to the European Commission late in 2022.

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Thank you and best wishes from the IMMERSE [Ireland team at University College Cork]!

[Shirley Martin – Primary Investigator
Deirdre Horgan – Co-Investigator
Jacqui O’Riordan – Co-Investigator
Reana Maier – Postdoctoral Researcher]

Support Resources in [Ireland]:

[list of resources and contact information here, about 3-5 organisations]

4.4 In-Person Site Visit Flow Chart

Pre and During Site Visit

Post -Site Visit

5 Alternative Data Collection Strategies for Covid-19

Due to Covid-19, research sites, particularly schools, may have re-opened and be conducting in-class learning, but may not be allowing visitors or guests to be physically present. They may also be conducting remote learning, with students working from home. While in-person visits are the preferred scenario, we do not recommend postponing all data collection until in-person visits will be possible simply because we have no way of knowing when this will be. Where in-person site visits are not possible for the foreseeable future, we encourage teams to consider one of the following alternatives for remote data collection: 'virtual' visits or open time frame data collection. Conducting data collection through these methods will obviously be different from in-person visits though will require as much negotiation and planning as in-person visits. Policies and preferences will be different from country to country, region to region, even site to site, so you must work with each site to determine what the best course of action will be.

5.1 'Virtual' Site Visits

In this scenario, data is collected from the children at the research site or in their homes, if the site is conducting learning remotely. Either way, the data collection is done during a single session lasting a few hours and facilitated by someone from the research site and 'virtually' by a member of the research team. This is basically the same format as a site visit as described in the previous section, but the researchers are not physically present. However, we suggest that, if possible, the researcher arrange to be present virtually through a platform such as Zoom or Skype or even over the phone (on speaker). This is so that the researcher can address the participants directly, introduce the study and questionnaire (sample script in section 3.2.1 below), remain online (or on the phone) during the data collection to answer any questions that may arise, and say thank you at the end. This option can be used whether the children are completing their questionnaires through the online data collection platform or using the PAP versions. If the children are using the PAP versions, you will need to get them to the site somehow and collect them from the site once the session is over.

5.1.1 Pre-site visit considerations

Unless otherwise stated, the pre-site visit guidelines for in-person visits should still be followed, but we have noted here a number of areas that will be affected by moving to a virtual visit.

RECRUITMENT

Recruitment is largely unaffected by moving to a virtual visit strategy, except that your introductory communication will outline what a virtual visit will entail, rather than what an in-

person site visit would entail (see example excerpt below). In-person follow-up meetings will not be an option.

Participation involves selecting several classes from [list the year groups you want to survey from that school, e.g. 1st/3rd/5th years in your school] to fill out a questionnaire, preferably online. There are also online questionnaires for the principal and teachers. We will provide a link to send to parents so they can give consent online and fill out a short questionnaire themselves. If parents give consent, we will collect data from the children. We understand that due to Covid-19, you may not be allowing guests into the [research site] at this time, and we have options available to conduct the survey without researchers being physically present. We will work with you to arrange a 'virtual' visit at the [site]'s convenience and ensure this takes as little time and causes as little disruption to normal activities as possible. We will provide detailed information about the survey and how the data will be collected, stored, and analysed.

SCHEDULING THE SITE VISIT

Calendar organisation, classroom sampling, site code, and sending links guidelines are unaffected by moving to a virtual visit.

Scheduling for a virtual visit would be done in a similar fashion to in-person visits, but you obviously will not need to take into account any travel concerns, unless someone on the team would personally be delivering and collecting PAP versions. If sites (mainly schools) are conducting online classes with the children while they are at home, you might discuss with the site the possibility of using one of these sessions to have the children complete the questionnaire.

Helpful information to gather from the site

Information needed from the site is largely similar to an in-person visit. You can create a checklist or google form if you think this will be helpful.

- Does the site need PAP consent forms/parent questionnaires? If the site does not have an email distribution list of parents or parents are unlikely to be able to get online to give consent and fill out their questionnaire, you will need to arrange for PAP forms to be delivered to the site and distributed to parents (check with site about which languages would be appropriate).
- Approximately how many participants in total from whom you will be collecting data. This will give you an idea of how long the virtual visit last and, if necessary, how many PAP versions to send/deliver if site does not have tech/internet. For the PAP backups, check with the school to see which languages would be useful to send.
- What technology the site has available for the online data collection – computers, laptops, tablets – including what technology the children may bring of their own. If they do not have tech available, you will need to arrange to provide them with PAP versions of the questionnaires.

- Whether there is a stable internet connection, preferably Wi-Fi. If the site does not have an internet connection, you will have to provide the site with PAP versions. There is an offline data collection platform, but it has to be downloaded via an internet connection. This is really only an option for in-person visits where the research team are bringing in their own devices. In addition, if the site does not have stable internet, you may have to conduct your visit over the phone (speakerphone) rather than via a video conference platform.
- Who is the contact person at the site if one of the children experiences distress during the data collection and any site policies related to this. For a virtual visit, it would be a good idea to discuss this with whoever at the site will be facilitating the data collection session.

PRE-SITE VISIT CHECKLIST

For a virtual visit, we still suggest having a meeting with the team members who will be doing data collection to go over logistics, with an altered pre-site visit checklist:

- Date and time of visit confirmed with site 24-48 hours ahead of visit, arrange to meet with facilitator at the site before session begins to test video conference platform is working
- Check online to see whether parental consents have been given
- Check with site for PAP parental consents where necessary, will have to mailed or physically collected
- Check with site to ensure PAP questionnaires are on-site where necessary
- Review the timeline of the site visit
- Assign responsibilities to members of research team

An inventory list will not be useful for virtual visits, though you will still need to keep a logbook.

5.1.2 During a Virtual Visit

SITE LOGBOOK

Below is an example of how to adapt a logbook entry for a virtual visit.

Site Visit Logbook Entry # 18	
Site: Hogwarts	Site code: 02
Date: 23 November, 2020	Location: Dublin
Research team: Reana via Zoom	
Time of arrival at site: 9:30am	Time of departure from site: 12:30pm

Group No.	No. of part's	Year/ age group	Length of time to complete questionnaire	Length of time for debrief	Problems arising	How problems were addressed
1	25	1st year (12/13 year olds)	40 minutes	5 minutes	Trouble understanding Q. X	Explained using alternate language
2	30	3 rd year (14/15 year olds)	40 minutes	5 minutes	Log in page wouldn't work	Reloaded site
3	20	5 th year (16/17 year olds)	35 minutes	5 minutes		

During the process of arranging the virtual visit, you will know whether the site has the technology and internet connection necessary for you to be 'present' via a video conference platform or via phone (preferably on speaker phone at least for the introduction and debrief/thank you).

As with in-person visits, be sure to confirm with the person who is coordinating/facilitating your visit who the designated contact person is if a child experiences distress and how that person can be contacted quickly. We recommend, if possible, meeting with the facilitator with enough time to make sure the video conference platform is working and to set up the space in which the data collection will take place so that when the participants arrive, you can go straight into introducing the study and questionnaires.

ADMINISTERING THE SURVEY

The introductory script is largely unaffected by moving to a virtual visit, except that you may want to explain why you're not able to be there in person.

In terms of administering the survey, either online or in PAP form, because you are not able to be physically present, you will have to rely on the person at the site who is facilitating the session to help you get the participants started and to resolve any issues that arise, such as assisting the children to get to the right screen to start the questionnaire or handling participant distress. Again, ensure before the session starts that you and the facilitator know who to contact in cases of participant distress. We also recommend having the data collection platform user guide handy in case of technical problems.

If you are on a portable device, such as a tablet, laptop, or mobile phone you may want to ask the facilitator to bring it (and you) to any participant who has questions while filling out the questionnaire. If you are not on a portable device, the participants would have to come to where you "are" in the room to ask their question. Volume should be set at such a level as to reduce the likelihood of other participants being able to overhear. For ethical reasons, it is

not advisable to have questions relayed to you from the participant through the facilitator, but each situation is different, and we encourage teams to use their best judgement in the field.

At the end of the session, we suggest a short debrief, the same as for an in-person visit.

EXITING THE SITE

At the end of the virtual visit, confirm with the facilitator whether there are any PAP consent forms, parent questionnaires, and children's questionnaires that need to be sent/collected and how this will be done. As with an in-person site visit, thank the person who coordinated the site visit and leave them with your contact information should they have any questions or concerns. Advise them that you will follow-up in a few days to make sure everything is alright and on how to keep updated on the project's progress.

5.1.3 Post-site visit

Post-site visit activity guidelines are largely the same for a virtual visit as for an in-person visit. You will not have to worry about manual upload of data from offline devices, as the site will not be able to use the offline version of the data collection platform. If PAP questionnaires were used, you will need to manually input data from PAP questionnaires after these have been collected from the site.

Data checks, follow-ups and thank-yous can proceed as outlined for an in-person visit.

5.1.4 Virtual Site Visit Flow Chart

Pre- and During Virtual Site Visit

Post-Virtual Site Visit

5.2 Open Time Frame Data Collection at Participant’s Convenience

Another option for remote data collection is to allow the children to complete their questionnaire at any time and any location that is convenient for them, as we are doing with the parents, principals, and teachers. In this scenario, there is no site visit, in-person or virtual, so procedures for this option are quite different.

As you will see from the sections below, this method may be appealing to both sites and researchers. It places less of a burden on the sites, because it doesn't require them to give up any of their own time for the data collection, which may make them more likely to agree to participate. Researchers are not committed to a long data collection session during which they will be "on" all the time and would also be able to have data collection going on at multiple sites simultaneously.

On the other hand, this strategy gives the research team the least amount of control over data collection conditions for the children. Researchers would not necessarily be available to answer participant questions, and we have no way of knowing what kind of environment the children will be in when they fill out their questionnaire. There is a potential ethical concern with parents being present while children fill out their questionnaires at home, possibly influencing (however unintentionally) how the children respond to certain questions. This is a particular concern for the younger children who may well need a great deal of help to complete the questionnaire. Allowing participants to complete the questionnaire on their own time also requires the researchers to wait for 1-2 weeks for data to be gathered, as opposed to a single morning or afternoon, and may not yield as high of response rates as single sessions facilitated by the site.

We therefore recommend this option only for sites with older children (10-18 years) AND if the site is not willing to engage in either in-person or virtual site visits.

5.2.1 Pre-data collection considerations

RECRUITMENT

Open time frame data collection should not be the first option offered to sites when recruiting. We recommend using the same kind of introductory communication as for a virtual visit, and if this is refused by the site, then consider suggesting the alternative of open time frame data collection.

Follow-ups can proceed in basically the same fashion except that in-person follow-up meetings will obviously not be a possibility.

ARRANGING THE SITE VISIT

If the site will only agree to open time frame data collection, please note the following guidelines for setting up this type of data collection. Classroom sampling and site codes are unaffected.

Scheduling for this type of data collection is both more and less cumbersome than scheduling single data collection sessions. You do not need to agree on a date with the site, and you do not need to prepare someone at the site to facilitate the session. However, instead of being accomplished in a single morning/afternoon, data collection from the children will last a few weeks and will not have a researcher with them, in person or virtually,

to answer questions. In this scenario, because participants could be filling out questionnaires at literally any time, it is impractical to offer to have a researcher contactable at all times to answer questions immediately. To mitigate the problem of participant questions, however, you could advise that a researcher will be available to answer questions during set days and times and recommend to your participants that they fill out their survey during those times in case they have a question and need to contact the researcher. Contact can be via email, phone, or video conference, whatever your team feels will be most comfortable and effective for both the researcher and the participant.

We recommend setting the data collection period for children's questionnaires at 1-2 weeks. Including the time allowed for parents to give consent and fill out their questionnaires (2-3 weeks), this means that data collection from a single site could be going on for approximately a month.

Helpful information to gather from the site

- Does the site need PAP consent forms/parent questionnaires? If the site does not have an email distribution list of parents or parents are unlikely to be able to get online to give consent and fill out their questionnaire, you will need to arrange for PAP forms to be delivered to the site and distributed to parents (check with site about languages needed).
- Approximately how many participants in total from whom you will be collecting data. This will help you gauge how many responses to expect.
- What technology are participants likely to have access to in order to fill in their questionnaires? If participants are unlikely to have access to technology, you will need to provide PAP versions to the site to distribute to the children. For the PAP back-ups, check with the site to see which languages would be useful to send.
- Whether participants will also have a stable internet connection, preferably Wi-Fi. If they likely do not have an internet connection, you will have to provide the site with PAP versions to distribute. There is an offline data collection platform but it has to be previously downloaded in order to access it. This is really only an option for in-person visits where the research team are bringing in their own devices. If participants do not have an internet connection, they will have to use the PAP versions.

PRE-DATA COLLECTION CHECKLIST

You may still want to have meetings and checklists in place for open time frame data collection, though perhaps placed before the link for parental consent/questionnaire is sent to the site or before you open the data collection period for the children. Below are some suggestions for a check list:

- Dates of data collection period confirmed
- Check online to see whether parental consents have been given

- Check with site for PAP parental consents where necessary, will have to mailed or physically collected
- Check with site to ensure PAP questionnaires are on-site where necessary
- Confirm dates and times of ‘help sessions’ where researchers are available to answer questions, check these have been communicated to participants through site
- Assign responsibilities to members of research team

An inventory list will not be useful for open time frame data collection, though you will still need to keep a logbook.

5.2.2 During the data collection period

As there is no site visit, per se, you won’t need to go through many of the during-site visit procedures outlined in Section 3, such as an introductory script and debrief. You should still keep a log of the data collection periods and ‘help sessions’ with any problems that arose.

SAMPLE SITE VISIT LOGBOOK ENTRY FOR OPEN TIME FRAME DATA COLLECTION

Site Visit Logbook Entry # 18	
Site: Hogwarts	Site code: 02
Date: 16 Nov – 20 Dec, 2020	Location: Dublin
Research team: Reana, Jacqui, Deirdre	
Link for parent, principal, & teachers sent: 16 November	Deadline: 30 November
Link for children sent: 30 November	14 December

Dates of ‘help sessions’	Problems arising during session	How problem was addressed
30 Nov 3pm-5pm		
2 Dec 10am-12pm		
3 Dec 6pm-8pm		

Once the data collection period closes, if participants filled in PAP versions, these will need to be collected.

5.2.3 Post-data collection

Post-data collection guidelines are largely the same for open time frame data collection as for an in-person or virtual visit. You will not have to worry about manual upload of data from offline devices, as the site will not be able to use the offline version of the data collection platform. If PAP questionnaires were used, you will need to manually input data from PAP questionnaires after these have been collected from the site.

Data checks, follow-ups and thank-yous can proceed as outlined for an in-person visit.

5.2.4 Open Time Frame Data Collection Flow Chart

Pre- and During Data Collection

Post Data Collection

6 Appendices

6.1 Appendix A – Participant ID Codes

Participant ID codes are the anonymous identifiers we will attach to the data gathered from our participants in order to organise and analyse it. The ID codes will contain information on the country, region/city, and school the participant is in, but nothing about the identity of the participant.

We are using a 12-character alpha-numeric system with the following pattern:

*Each team will need to assign these codes to their regions and provide this list to IECISA.

**Each team would assign numbers to the schools they are visiting for data collection and keep a key (e.g. school 02 = Hogwarts, school 59 = Xavier’s School for Gifted Youngsters, etc.). We advise a random system of assigning numbers to the schools. The key would not be shared outside that team and would not be included in any documentation on the project to help preserve anonymity.

We will need each team to provide IECISA with a list of their region/city codes. As part of the consent process, parents will indicate the country they are in (from a list), the city/region (from a list), and the 2-digit code for the school their child attends (to be included in the information letter).